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Effect of Generative-Learning-Strategy on Achievement in Probability Concept among Secondary School Mathematics Students in Sabon-Tasha Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the Effect of Generative-Learning-Strategy on Achievement in probability concept among Secondary School Students in Sabon-Tasha educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The research design adopted for the study was quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test, posttest experimental and control group design. The population of the study was 62,072 Secondary School class Two (SS II) Mathematics students in Sabon-Tashah Educational zone of Kaduna State. The sample of the study was 455 Mathematics students' drawn from four sample senior secondary schools through purposive sampling procedure. Two (2) research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. Probability Attitude Test (PAT) was used for data collection. The internal consistency of PAT was obtained using Kuder Richardson formula 20(KR-20), Hence, Reliability coefficients of 0.93 were obtained for the PAT. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. Results showed that Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) was more effective in improving students' academic achievement in Probability Concept than the Conventional Method of Teaching (CMT). The study concludes that the findings of this

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study demonstrate that the use of GLS significantly improves students' academic achievement probability concepts. GLS was also found to be gender friendly and the study recommended adequate training of teachers on the use of GLS for Nigerian Secondary Schools amongst others.

Keyword: Generative Learning Strategy, Attitude, Mathematics Concepts, Probability and Students

Introduction

Mathematics can be described as the study of space, time, sequence, pattern, structures, among others, in solving human problems. Ogbu (2020) opined that the high level of development of mathematics was assumed to have been sparked by the needs of the society and its competence is vital to everyone for meaningful understanding of things and situations. Anaduaka and Hassan (2017) viewed mathematics as the oldest field of study in the history of mankind and the most central component of human thought. Mathematics sharpens the mind, develops logical thinking and enhances the reasoning ability of an individual. Researchers, such as Cabe Roya (2010), Ogunleye and Babajide (2011) affirmed that the use of Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) is effective and results oriented. Hence, the use of Generative Learning Strategy as a means of improving students' achievement in mathematics through classroom activity aimed at enhancing students' greater comprehension and higher order thinking skills in mathematics is advocated.

Similarly, Adesoji (2008) defined students' achievement as the outcomes that reflect the extent to which an individual has attained a specific goal within instructional environments, particularly in schools, colleges, and universities. However, students' achievement should be viewed as a multifaceted construct encompassing various domains of learning. According to Okeke (2011), several criteria indicate students' achievement, including procedural and declarative knowledge acquired within an educational system. Consequently, there is a need to adopt Generative Learning Strategies to create a conducive and enriching environment that motivates, enhances attitudes, and improves students' achievement in the probability concept of mathematics at the senior secondary school level.

Gender as a factor needs to be investigated as one of the moderating variables in this study. School environment and educational facilities can make a great impact in terms of students' achievement in mathematics. This study therefore, was designed to investigate the effect of Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) on achievement

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in Probability Concepts among Secondary School Mathematics Students in Sabon-Tasha educational Zone, Kaduna State.

Statement of the Research Problem

The problem of poor attitude in mathematics has continued to resurface yearly in public examinations in Nigeria. The SSCE results released by WAEC and NECO have remained consistently poor and worrisome. The WAEC Chief Examiner's report identified probability concept as one of the students' areas of weaknesses. It further stated that the majority of the students attempted probability questions wrongly because of poor knowledge of the concept; inability to interpret problems involved the concept of probability, inability to read value from the problem which also involved the concept of probability. (WAEC, 2019; 2021 & 2022). Bababjide, 2011 and Amal & Elfateh, 2016). Their findings revealed that students exposed to Generative Learning Strategy performed better than their counterparts in the control group. Although a few studies on the use of Generative Learning Strategy have been carried out in the sciences in Nigeria, the extent of the use of Generative Learning Strategy has not been fully confirmed in the area of mathematics in Nigerian but elsewhere. Garba (2021) has shown that the use of probability concepts in teaching mathematics can improve students' academic achievement and retention in learning mathematics. This study therefore, is designed to examine the effect of Generative Learning Strategy on achievement of probability concept among Secondary School Mathematics students in Kaduna State.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study was to examine the effect of Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) on achievement in Probability Concepts among Secondary School Mathematics Students in Sabon-Tasha educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the difference in the achievement of students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those taught using the conventional teaching method in the Sabon-Tasha Educational Zone.
2. Investigate the difference in the achievement of male and female students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) in the Sabon-Tasha Educational Zone.

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Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the achievement of students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those exposed to conventional methods?
2. What is the difference in the achievement of male and female students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS)?

Null Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the achievement of students taught probability using Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those exposed to conventional methods in Sabon-Tashah Educational Zone.
2. There is no significant difference in the achievement of male and female students taught probability using Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) in Sabon-Tashah Educational Zone.

Research Design

The research design adopted for the study was quasi-experimental pretest posttest control group design. (Lauren Thomas, 2023) see quasi-experimental design as a useful tool in situations where true experiments cannot be used for ethical or practical reasons. This design is appropriate because the researcher assigned subjects to treatment and control conditions; but used intact classes to assign the groups so as to avoid the disruption of the normal class periods. The design was necessary also because it is appropriate for analyzing gain scores (i.e. the difference between pre-test and post-test scores) in addition to comparing scores. The layout of the design is shown below

EG → Q₁ → X₁ → Q₂ → Q₃: CG → Q₁ → - → Q₂ → Q₃

Where:

EG – Experimental Group

CG – Control Group

Q₁ – Represents the pre-test on the experimental group and Control group

Q₂ – Represent the post-test on the experimental group and Control group

X₁– Treatment for experimental group

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Q₃ – Retention test for experimental and control group

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised Sixty-two thousand and seventy-two (62,072) SS II students in all the 1,018 Government owned Senior Secondary Schools in Kaduna State. This comprises 29,057 male and 33,015 female SS II students (Kaduna State Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sample size of the study was 455 Senior Secondary II students drawn from four sampled schools (Government Senior Secondary School, Bagodo, Government Secondary School Kakuri, Government Secondary School Angwan Boro and Government Senior Secondary School, Narayi) within the study area. Four (4) schools from the educational zone (Kaduna South Local Government Area and Chikun South Local Government Area) that made up the study area were selected through random sampling method by balloting. This allowed for a fair chance of being selected.

Secondly, the four (4) schools were subjected to another round of balloting by picking from a container with four (4) papers was also tagged “YES” and others “NO” on squeezed pieces of paper for selection. Representatives of the four (4) Schools were allowed to pick on their behalf. The four (4) “YES” Schools were used for the research sample. Thirdly, two (2) schools out of the four (4) Schools were assigned to the experimental group (treatment group) while the last two (2) Schools formed the control group by random sampling (toss of coin).

The distribution of research subjects in their intact classes for this study is shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Sample Distribution

Group	Name of School	Male	Female	Total
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Experimental Group	GSS Narayi	62	53	115
	GSS Kakuri	67	51	118
Control Group	GSS Bagodo	76	48	124
	GSS U/Boro	57	41	98
Total		262	193	455

Instrumentation

The instruments that were used to collect data for the study was Probability Attitude Scale (PAS). Both instruments were constructed by the researcher and used as pre-test and post-test in the study. The PAS was of 20 items, 4-Options Multiple Choice Objective test based on the content of probability concept in in SS II Mathematics as shown in table of specification Probability Attitude Scale (PAS) was made up of two Sections: Section A contains Personal information and Section B contains Items and instruction for ticking the chosen response for each item. The PAS formed a 30 items Attitude Inventory developed by the researcher. It has a 4–point scale response. The responses are Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD).The respondents were expected to indicate the degree of their agreement and disagreement on a number of statements (positive or negative) equal cues about the units of study in probability concept.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

The PAS was validated by the experts in science education and Mathematics Education, Department of Science and Environmental Education, Faculty of Education, University of Abuja. Their validations were centered in terms of clarity of instruments, correct wordings of items, appropriateness and adequacy of the items in addressing the purpose and problem of the study. The experts’ appraisal and comments were used to reform the items for the final package of the instrument used for the study. In measuring the reliability of the instruments for this study, the instruments: PAS were pilot tested using 15 SS II students of Government Secondary School Sabon-Tasha, Chikun LGA, Kaduna State who were part of the population but not part of the sample of the study. They were randomly selected. An hour was allowed for the test. The scripts were collated, marked and scored. Responses in PAS were also used to calculate the reliability coefficient of the PAS using Cronbach alpha procedures. The reliability coefficients for the PAS obtained was 0.92

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Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher personally visited the selected schools with letter of introduction collected from the Head of Department of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria. The letter was given to the Principals and Head of Departments of the selected schools seeking permission to engage their students and mathematics teachers in a study. The researchers interacted with the students' and informed them of the purpose of the study and the benefits they are likely to gain from the study. Also, the consent form was issued to the participating students' and the teachers to indicate their willingness in the study in line with the standard of research practices.

The researcher trained the selected mathematics teachers as research assistants who touched the experimental group using GLS. The control groups were taught by mathematics teachers in the schools. The control group were taught without the use of GLS In the experimental group, the researcher grouped the students in the group heterogeneously based on their achievement in their terminal examination. The class consisted of five or six students in each group. The sitting arrangement was re-constructed in a semi- circular form to make it possible for the GLS learning and for the teacher to move across the groups. The seats were arranged for all the students to face the chalkboard. The students were assigned defined roles to two members of the group (group leader and the time keeper) while others served as secretary, in order to record what has been learnt in the group.

Method of Data Analysis

The six research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation while the six null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The ANCOVA was appropriate for the study because it determined the differential effect of the treatment with the pretest scores as covariates to control the initial group difference. (comparing pretest scores with post-test scores to determine whether any significant difference occurs as a consequence of GLS and CMT). ANCOVA was appropriate for the study because it served as a procedure for increasing the precision due to extraneous variables that could have affected the external validity thus reducing error variance).

Answers to Research Questions

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Research Question One: What is the difference in the achievement of students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those exposed to conventional methods?

To answer this research question, descriptive statistics was computed as recorded in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students’ achievement Pretest and Posttest Scores level by Learning Strategies (Experimental and control)

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean	Mean
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Gain	Difference
Experimental	233	24.72	1.93	30.00	3.91	5.28	3.21
Control	222	23.53	2.34	25.60	2.22	2.07	
Total	455	24.14	2.22	27.85	3.88		

Table 2 shows a mean achievement pretest level of 24.72 with a standard deviation of 1.93 for students taught probability concepts using generative learning Strategy and a Mean achievement Pretest level of 23.53 with a standard deviation of 2.34 for students taught using conventional method of teaching. As for the posttest, the table also shows a posttest mean achievement level of 30.00 with a standard deviation of 3.91 for students taught using generative learning strategy and a mean achievement level of 25.60 with a standard deviation of 2.22 for students taught using conventional method of teaching. The students taught probability concepts using generative learning strategy had a higher achievement mean gain level of 5.28 compared to their counterparts that were taught using conventional methods of teaching who had an achievement Mean gain level of 2.07. Students taught probability concepts using generative learning strategies had a higher achievement mean score in posttest than those taught using conventional methods of teaching probability concepts. The difference in mean achievement level of students taught using generative learning Strategy and those taught with conventional methods of teaching was 3.21. Hence there is a difference in students’ achievement to probability concepts when taught with GLS and when taught with CMT. Thus, those in experimental groups showed higher achievement than those in control groups.

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Research Question two: What is the difference in the achievement of male and female students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS)?

To answer this research question, descriptive statistics was computed as recorded in Table 3

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' achievement Pretest and Posttest Level by Gender

Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain	Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Male	262	21.6145	1.8425	29.1450	2.9894	7.53	0.38
Female	193	21.6373	1.8152	29.5440	3.2161	7.91	
Total	455	21.6242	1.8290	29.3142	3.0904		

Table 3 shows a Mean achievement Pretest level of 21.6145 with a Standard Deviation of 1.8425 for Male Students taught probability concepts using Generative Learning Strategy and a Mean achievement Pretest level of 21.6373 with a Standard Deviation of 1.8152 for Female Students taught using Generative Learning Strategy. The Posttest shows a Mean achievement level of 29.1450 with a Standard Deviation of 2.9894 for Male Students taught using generative learning Strategy and a Mean achievement of 29.5440 with a Standard Deviation of 3.2161 for Female Students taught using Generative Learning Strategy. This indicates that the Mean achievement level of Male and Female Students' taught probability concepts using generative learning Strategy was slightly different. This means that the Mean achievement level of Male and Female Students were not influenced by Students' gender. The difference in mean achievement level of male and students taught using generative learning strategy was 0.38

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the achievement of students taught probability using Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those exposed to conventional method in Sabon-Tashah Educational Zone:

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Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Tests Level by Generative Learning Strategy (Experimental and Control group)

Dependent Variable: Posttest Score

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	2205.869 ^a	2	1102.935	107.814	.000	S
Intercept	3058.765	1	3058.765	298.999	.000	S
Pretest	8.348	1	8.348	.816	.367	N.S
Attitude	2111.499	1	2111.499	206.402	.000	S
Error	4623.968	452	10.230			
Total	359752.000	455				
Corrected Total	6829.837	454				

a. R Squared = .323 (Adjusted R Squared = .320)

Table 4 shows the Analysis of Covariance test analysis carried out to determine whether students taught using GLS and those taught with CMT differed significantly in their attitude level in probability concepts. This test resulted in F-value 206.402 for the group (Experimental and Control group) is significant at .000 which is less than 0.05 ($p < .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis stated was accepted. Thus, there is a significant difference in the achievement of students taught probability using GLS and those exposed to CMT. This implies that students taught with GLS had a higher attitude level than those that were taught with CMT.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude level of male and female students taught taught probability with GLS.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Test Level by Gender

Dependent Variable: Posttest Score

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	50.313 ^a	2	25.157	1.563	.211	N

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Intercept	3498.027	1	3498.027	217.340	.000	N.S
Pre	46.185	1	46.185	2.870	.091	N.S
Gender	7.225	1	7.225	.449	.503	N.S
Error	7274.821	452	16.095			
Total	367807.000	455				
Corrected Total	7325.134	454				

a. R Squared = .007 (Adjusted R Squared = .002)

Table 5 shows the Analysis of Covariance carried out to determine whether Male and Female Students taught probability concepts using GLS differed significantly in their attitude level in probability concepts. This test resulted in F-value .449 which is not significant at .503 which is above .001 ($p < 0.05$). The Null hypothesis as formulated was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the Mean attitude level of Male and Female Students taught probability concepts using GLS.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that the use of GLS significantly improves students' academic achievement probability concepts. Compared to the CTM, GLS proves to be more effective. This indicates that implementing GLS not only enhances students' performance but also positively influences their attitude toward probability concepts.

The effects of gender on mean attitude level, mean achievement score and mean retention score were not significant. Observed difference in attitude level, mean achievement score and retention score of students taught using GLS is due to chance not gender. However, contrary to conventional methods, GLS learning encourages learners to solve a particular problem or answer a central question using experience acquired from the GLS.

The GLS instruction helps learners to be actively involved in authentic, hands-on and natural learning in order to develop a new knowledge and apply the new knowledge to a new situation. Therefore, GLS is an appropriate strategy for teaching probability concepts.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since GLS is found to be an effective teaching strategy for improving student's mean achievement score, mean attitude score and mean retention score in

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- probability concepts, teachers should adopt it as a teaching strategy in Secondary Schools.
2. Bearing in mind the roles of workshops and seminars in the dissemination of knowledge and innovations, the researcher recommends that the Ministry of Education, MAN, STAN WAEC and JAMB should organize in-service training, workshops and seminars to equip teachers with necessary skills in the use of GLS.
 3. Authors and publishers of mathematics textbooks should include GLS in their texts for easy access for students and teachers and Curriculum planners also should include GLS in the Senior Secondary School mathematics Scheme for teachers and Students in order to enhance the participation, achievement, attitude and retention in students.
 4. Mathematics teachers should not introduce gender discrepancies when using GLS. They should as much as possible remove contents, instructional techniques and materials that may bring about gender differences in the teaching and learning of probability concepts.

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